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**THE RELEVANCE OF SIR THOMAS MUNRO IDEALS IN DISTRICT
ADMINISTRATION – A STUDY**

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Abstract

Thomas Munro remembered as a capable soldier and successful administrator. He rendered his services to Indians as a Soldier, as a Municipal Commissioner, as a Principal Collector, as a President of Administration of Justice, as a Governor of Madras, etc., . Munro is credited with having introduced the ryotwari system in South India and drafting an education policy for the Madras Presidency. Munro was the company's servant who devoted his life to the welfare of people. Here is a piece of historical research work on Munro administration which is ideal to modern government also. The people of Rayalaseema still cherish the memory of Munro though 208 years have passed away since his administration. That illustrious name has almost passed into a legend in the memory of the people of ceded Districts Munro is the subject of a number of local folk tales and songs and is even worshipped by some.

Key words: Administration, revenue settlement, law and order, collector,

1. Introduction:

The Collector was verily the British rule incarnate and regarded as father and mother of the District. Collector was the Principal administrator and his main duty was to collect the revenue. District Collector virtually acts as the eyes, ears and arms of the State Government. The problem of the officials was the language. They took the assistance of dubashis. They had to depend upon their subordinate staff, which often misguided them. They also indulged in corrupt practices. The only exceptional person was Munroe who spoke Telugu fluently and carried on the administration without the help of dubhashis during the East India Company rule.

1.1 Methodology:

For this research work We have depend on primary sources Records, circulars, Gazetteers in Anantapur District collectorate and some secondary sources of historical works of Gopal B.R, Triveni D, Sastri K.N.V.etc., History has not so far made clear is that he was the first man in the service of the company who opposed Corn Wallis system and offered alternative method of government. It was probably the most important founder of the liberal school of Indian Administration. He also supported a larger share for natives in the administration of India. In this regard we made little effort to fill the patches in historical gaps.

2. Munro's brief life sketch:

Thomas Munro was one of the most famous administrators in British India. He was born in Glasgow in 27th May 1761 in Briton. Munro started his career as a soldier in 1789 in India during the East India Company rule. He participated in the Third Anglo Mysore War. After the war, he served as a settlement officer at Baramahal in Canara region. And then he was appointed as Principal Collector for Ceded Districts. There he served for seven years. After his resignation in 1807 he went to England to take rest. Again he returned to India. He had shown his courage in the Pindari War in 1817. Munro was appointed as Madras Governor in 1820, and served till his death in 1827.

3. Thomas Munro as a Collector:

The East India Company started consolidating the position in the first half of the 19th century in India as well as in Andhra region. It reorganized the districts in Andhra region and appointed collectors to collect the revenue. The coastal area was divided into 5 Collectorates, Ganjam, Vishakhapatnam, Krishna and Nellore. The Rayalaseema area was brought under one collectorate with Anantapur as its head quarters.

In 1800 Nizam of Hyderabad entered into a Subsidiary alliance with the East India Company. By this treaty the company agreed to protect the Nizam by maintaining its army at Hyderabad. To meet the cost of these troops the Nizam ceded to the company the territories of Bellary, Anantapur, Cuddapah and Kurnool. Munro was appointed as the first and foremost Principal Collector of these districts.

3.1 Munro's District Administration:

Thomas Munro took charge on 24th October; 1800. It was more important period in his long official life. In the Baramahal District his position had been in a subordinate one. In canara where for the first time he was invested with an independent charge, his tenure office had been too short to admit of his doing more than to suppress disorder and to lay principles of administration which his successors could work out. Munro rendered his valuable services to the people of ceded Districts up to a period of 7 years (i.e., 24th October, 1800 to 23rd October 1807).

He was the supreme authority and the supervising authority over four Sub-Collectors. They were put in charge of Cuddapah, Kambam, Adoni and Harpana Halli. When Munro was the Principal Collector, he held charge of the taluks which now constitute the Anantapur District. Except C.P. Brown and Thomas Munroe, all other Collectors do not know Telugu language, so they have to depend upon the local people or on an employee known as Dubashee.

3.2. Suppression of polygars:

At that time Munro assumed charge of his new duties, the ceded districts were in a complete anarchy. There were eighty polygars in these areas. They with their 30,000 armed followers looted the villagers and created terror among the people. The local polygars created a state of lawlessness and indulged in internecine strife. So Polygars in Rayalaseema with their army used to give utmost troubles to the people through their way of administration.

Munro's Chief concern was to establish a well organized Government by subjugating polygars who infested these tracts. Munro first turned his attention to subdue the polygars and disbanded their armed followers. The polygars of Rayaseema revolted the British in 1800 since many of them were not ready to accept the suzerainty of the British the Principal Collector of the region, Thomas Munroe issued a proclamation to lay down their arms and

pay their Peshkhash to the company. Many of them resisted the demand and it took more than 18 months for him to bring them under control.

He took stringent measures against them and prohibited them from maintaining armed men and garrisoning any their forts. He pursued each delinquent who attempted the evasion of payment of rent and put him down. He pensioned off some like Siddappa, a member of the hande family and expelled others like the Palegar of Kammalalah. This process usually went off peacefully. It was only one occasion that there was open resistance to British authority.

He himself as a warrior gained a lot of experience, so he collected some people under his army, waged a war with polygars and defeated them and thus he brought happiness to the people. Gay and cheerfulness of people his cheerfulness. When he left his job as a collector there was not a trace of polygars.

3.3. Land revenue reforms:

After restoring law and order Munro commenced his work of survey and revenue settlement .In 1802 the survey of ceded districts commenced and was completed by 1807.The entire cultivated area of the region was surveyed a number was given to each field , the name of the holder was registered and assessment fixed. Munro was able to complete this work which was quiet new to him in a record time of five years.

This work is “on the whole wonderfully correct and thorough...it is even to this day a safe guide in most village disputes.”After completing the survey, he introduced the ryotwari system of land revenue which he first tried successfully in the Baramahals during the years 1792-99.

Before introducing the ryotwari system he introduced the village system .Each village was assessed at a certain valuation and cultivators held responsible for that sum .but before cultivation commenced in 1801-02, Munro made necessary advances to the ryots to purchase seeds, implements, bullocks and to repair old wells or dig new ones. This fact is enough to show Munro’s concern for the welfare of the ryot. In 1802 ceded districts suffered from drought and famines and in the next year there were heavy rains which breached 1000 tanks and 800 channels in the cuddapah district alone. Munro without waiting for the orders of the government ordered the repairs of the damaged tanks and channels. The repairs were so speedily affected that in the following year there was a bumper crop and government was able to collect total revenue.

3.4 Ryotwari Settlement:

Munro felt Ryotwari System is the most prominent one in land Tax System. He felt it fetches good income for the company and also growth of agriculture takes place. He surveyed the land in Ceded Districts and accordingly he imposed taxes and implemented Ryotwari System. In this the total land will measured and after surveying the land, taxes imposed on the basis of the fertility of the soil. Government officials collect the taxes directly by the farmers. There should be no mediator. By this system company's Income had been grown from 402,637 pounds to 906,909 pounds within 7 years. The growth of income is 504,272 pounds. Munro recommended several land revenue reforms to East India Company on which he got rich experience from Ceded District Administration.

3.5 Respect of local beliefs:

Munro had a lot of respect towards to the local traditions. Thomas Munro was ordered by the Madras Government in 1800, to procure the total income from the famous Raghavendra Swami Math and Manthralayam village. The local Revenue officials were unable to implement this order. Munro personally visited the local Math for investigation. When he entered into temple he followed local practice by removing his hat and shoes. A local story which gives a description that Sri Raghavendraswamy emerged from the Vrindavan and appeared only to Munro. He talked with Munro for little bit of time, on the resumption of endowment land and gave Manthraksha. Munro went back to his office and circulated an order in favour of the village and Math. This Official notification was published with the caption "Manchali Adoni Taluka" in the Madras Government Gazette in Chapter XI, page 213. The order is still preserved in Manthralayam temple and Fort St. George Madras.

3.6 Estimate of Thomas Munro's District Administration:

In the ceded districts he remained long enough to guide and direct the development of the system which he introduced and to habituate the people to the spectacle of a ruler who, with inflexible firmness in securing the just rights of the state and maintaining law and order, combined a patient and benevolent attention to the well being of all classes .It was while holding this charge that Munro thoroughly worked out the ryotwari system....throughout Madras and Bombay.

His compassion, his marvellous understanding of the people and their civilisation has magnanimous policy and his sleepless efforts to promote their welfare are still remembered in a land where the tradition of benign rulers is strong and good and conscientious administrators have not been rare in modern days.

Munro has some consideration, courtesy and sympathy towards the poor and ordinary farmers. So he put forth his efforts for the upliftment of these poor and ordinary farmers. He took immediate steps to help the people who were struck by famines. Certain times, he used to go to the distant places without any weapons. This marks his valour.

4. Munro's final journey:

After completion of his tenure as Madras Governor in 1827 he spends a few days farewell tour at Ananthapur and Gooty his previous administration centres. There Munro affected with Cholera. Munro condition deteriorated and he died on July 6, 1827 at Pattikonda. His body was cremated at a graveyard in Gooty. All sections of people in Madras city mourned as a public calamity on Munro's death. The government released a Gazette Extraordinary on July 9, 1827 with the message:

“His sound and vigorous understanding, his transcendent talents, his indefatigable application, his varied stores of knowledge, his attainments as an Oriental scholar, his intimate acquaintance with the habits and feelings of native soldiers and inhabitants generally, his patience, temper and facility of access and kindness of manner would have ensured him distinction in any line of employment. These qualities were admirably adapted to the duties which he had to perform in organizing the resources and establishing the tranquillity of those provinces where his latest breath has been drawn and where he has long been known with the appellation of the Father of the People”.

A fine statue of Munro erected at Chennai with public donation in 1839. The Madras government started a memorial for Munro in Pattikonda. "Munro Choultry" was constructed in Gooty; his remains were shifted to Madras and interred at the St. Mary's Church in 1831. His residence at Ananthapur and wall its compound area now preserved as ancient Monuments.

5. Conclusion:

Though he came from foreign land he develops attachment to the people and place. Munro with his simple manners and concern for the welfare of the people won the hearts of one and all. Among the foreigners, Sir Thomas Munroe was one who could grasp the matters of India and Indian people. He is now shining like a glittering diamond across the Indian Sky. No wonder he was regarded as Mandava rishi and boys were named after him as munrolappa.

As a Soldier his Valour and courage, as a Warrior helped him to be rewarded by the British Parliament. This helped him for his growth of glory but this does not account for his permanent glory. His kind heartedness and administration are only important ones which brought him fame and name.

A benevolent administrator, he constructed tanks in and around Tadipatri and also made grants to temples for their maintenance. He endeared himself in variety of ways to the people of the district who continue to cherish loving memories to him.

Thus his administrative thoughts, ideals on strict maintenance of law and order, protecting common people rights, concern over public grievances, quick decisions in emergency conditions, attachment to natives, frequent field visits and raising income resources to government are more and more relevant today in any District's Administration throughout the World.

Notes:

1. Dubashis: translator of local language and interpretation to administrators
2. Rayalaseema: area comprising four districts in Andhrapradesh state
3. Polygars: petty local chiefs or rulers in Rayalaseema region in Andhrapradesh state
4. Ryotwari system: revenue collecting method during British rule in India
5. Ryot: farmers or peasants
6. Choultry: satram or local office room
7. Taluk: a Sub-division of District
8. Nizam: Ruler of Hyderabad state
9. Manyam: Land granted free of revenue
10. Ceded districts: Bellary, Anantapur, Cuddapah and Kurnool Districts of Madras Presidency

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